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On the feasibility of predicting current and wave conditions at deep water off the shelf break

Some event studies with application to Ormen Lange and
recommendation for further research activities

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1 Introduction

The exploration of hydrocarbons have in recent years been directed more and more towards deep water beyond the continental margins. This involves new challenges as the environmental forces on e.g. moorings and risers will, to a greater extent, be dominated by the currents.

The currents at the shelf edge and along the continental slopes are generally subjected to a wide range of dynamical activities. This is due to the fact that such a pronounced change in bottom topography acts as a converter for on-off shelf exchange processes. It is also an efficient trap for a number of wave phenomena. As an example, tides are generated in the deep oceans and propagate towards the shelf zones. As the tidal wave progress over the shelf slope it is gradually converted from weaker currents to stronger currents. Under favourable conditions this is accompanied by formation of internal waves that under given conditions can disintegrate into solitary waves. See Siedler et al. (2001) for a description of the general ocean circulation and Huthnance (1992, 1995) for further descriptions of shelf edge and shelf slope phenomena.

It has been a general opinion that currents in the deep oceans are fairly weak. However, so far the focus has been more on general flow and mean transports rather than on peak events in oceanography. This has also been the case for WOCE (World Ocean Circulation Experiment) Siedler et al. (2001). For the time and space mean circulation, the velocities are generally small, less than a few cms^{-1} , in the deep ocean.

To this standard picture of large gyres in each of the ocean basins, pictures of patchy mixing processes, topographically steered jets and variability are, however, emerging. See the chapter on the interior circulation of the ocean in Siedler et al. (2001). In Hansen and Østerhus (2000) velocities larger than 100 cms^{-1} through the Faroe bank Channel are reported. The time series from the offshore gas field Ormen Lange (OL) located in the Storegga region off mid-Norway at water depths from approximately 800m to 1100m, see Figure 1, also show that the velocities during peak events may exceed 50 cms^{-1} , see Mathisen (2001) and Eliassen et al. (2000). Often rapid changes in the flow are seen, and since the recorded velocities are time filtered, the true maximum velocities may be underestimated at present. The observational networks have so far not been dense enough to resolve all important length scales, and there are large geographical variations in the flow. There may, therefore, be areas where we get intensification and speeds exceeding 100 cms^{-1} also at OL. Such flows may create strong drags on risers, pipelines or mooring lines that may be of concern for offshore operations and development.

Since 1999 our research groups at the Mathematics Department, Univer-

sity of Bergen, and the Nansen Center have in cooperation with Norsk Hydro tried to understand currents and waves at OL. The approach has been to:

- a) Study relevant theory and papers for the Norwegian Sea and specially those parts dealing with the shelf edge and shelf slope off mid-Norway.
- b) Study general theory for shelf edge and shelf slope processes.
- c) Apply numerical models to estimate the currents and current profiles at OL.
- d) Apply numerical models to understand the underlying processes and their impact on the currents.
- e) Analyse available time series of currents and hydrography from OL.

The objectives of the studies have been to improve the understanding of off shelf current systems and subsequently use this knowledge as support for offshore operations and construction of design current profiles. We have used the Ormen Lange/Storegga area as a study site. Access to time series of currents and temperature at OL and to long time series at the Svinøy section (Orvik et al., 2001), through cooperation with the Geophysics Department, UiB, has been very important.

The results so far have been published in a series of technical reports (Eliassen and Berntsen, 2000; Eliassen et al., 2000; Heggelund and Berntsen, 2000, 2001). The ocean model applied in these studies has been described in Berntsen (2000). More recently a non-hydrostatic ocean model developed at MIT has been applied to study flow around local topography at OL Marshall et al. (1997b,a). At present work on a number of manuscripts describing on-going activity and results are in progress, Vikebø et al. (2001a,c,b); Avlesen and Berntsen (2001); Sørflaten and Berntsen (2001); Thiem et al. (2001). There is also on-going activities at the Geophysics Department (Orvik, Skagseth and Østerhus) on analysing time series of currents and hydrography from OL and the surrounding ocean.

In the present report we will try to summarise what we today regard as the major forcing mechanisms. We will discuss their effects on the flow and waves. Based on the present understanding of how the oceanic system at OL works, a possible monitoring system that may be used to predict major events a few days ahead will be described. A discussion of areas where further research and developments are needed to improve our understanding of the mechanisms behind events with large velocities and to design a possible monitoring system will be given.

Ormen Lange is used as a study area in our activities, but the methods may be applied to any sea region given that the topography and necessary input data are available.

2 Major forces and their effects at Ormen Lange

The time mean current at OL is strongly dominated by the Norwegian Atlantic Current (NAC). Close to the shelf edge this mean current is approximately 30 cm s^{-1} . At 800m depth the mean is approximately 5 cm s^{-1} , see Orvik et al. (2001). Tidal effects are weak i.e. less than 5 cm s^{-1} at these depths, but increasing towards the shelf edge. In the upper say 100m the flow is strongly affected by the atmospheric pressure and wind. At intermediate depths the flow is strongly directed along the general topography. In the bottom layer the flow is strongly affected by the roughness of the topography and is much more directional unstable (Vikebø et al., 2001a). The extreme events are driven by strong pressure gradients. That is: Strong atmospheric low pressures and/or internal pressure gradients at fronts between warmer Atlantic water (AW) and colder Norwegian Sea Arctic Intermediate Water (NSAIW). Along the shelf slope at OL steepening of the iso surfaces of density separating AW and NSAIW may occur due to strong Ekman veering

Figure 1: Ormen Lange - Storegga. The yellow curve outlines the gas field, and the red lines show considered pipe line tracks. Figure by courtesy of Jan Erik Sikkeland.

during storms and/or approaching internal density fronts. Figure 2 describes the water masses along the shelf off mid-Norway. During such events the density surfaces tend to undershoot their equilibrium level, and as the forcing weakens, the suppressed water may run up along the shelf slope. In this run up phase peak values in the velocities are often found. During run up colder and heavier water masses are lifted up on the shelf. As the wave off shelf retreats some of this heavy water on shelf may be separated from the water mass it originated from. This heavy on shelf water mass may follow the general flow along the shelf and, later on, flow down cross shelf canyons and create gravity currents. After front passages the oscillations of these density surfaces may continue for days, but their amplitudes will gradually decrease. A cartoon of these processes is given in Figure 3.

Figure 2: The water masses in the region divided into four different layers; Norwegian Coastal Water (NCW), Atlantic Water (AW), Norwegian Sea Arctic Intermediate Water (NSAIW) and Norwegian Sea Deep Water (NSDW).

Figure 3: A plausible model explaining the events occurring in the time series from Ormen Lange. The model is divided into three different phases; pre-conditioning, 'run-ups' and gravity currents.

3 Prediction of currents and waves

Gradients in the pressure create acceleration of water masses. This is essential in the Reynolds averaged momentum equations, and in agreement with our model experiments and analysis of measurements so far.

To be able to predict major events in velocities at OL, one must therefore predict peaks in pressure gradients.

Forecasts of atmospheric low pressure are routinely produced and these are trustworthy up to at maximum one week ahead.

There are major events that apparently are not linked to atmospheric pressure gradients, at least not on a short time scale. To predict internal pressure gradients in the ocean, one must have an array of current meter and hydrographic moorings surrounding OL. Assuming that the internal pressure fronts are propagated with the speed of the water masses, approximately 20 cms^{-1} , they move approximately 50 to 100 km over 5 days. Along such fronts there will be eddies and filaments. A typical length scale of these phenomena will be the internal Rossby radius which is 5 to 10 km in our area. To capture each internal eddy and filament propagating towards OL accurately will require an array of moorings along the circle around OL with radius 100km and a distance of approximately 1km between each mooring. That is more than 600 moorings. This is probably not feasible. However, by having a few moorings upstream in the general flow direction, south/south-west, one may be able to capture major fronts moving towards OL without capturing the details on the front. In addition with a hydrographic station 100km upstream from OL on the shelf, one may be able to detect possible cores of dense and cold water flowing towards OL that may create dangerous downslope gravity currents.

Thus with an observing system including:

- a) atmospheric weather forecasts,
- b) an array of 4 to 5 current and hydrographic moorings on a circle with radius $\sim 100\text{km}$ around OL reporting in real time,
- c) online ocean weather forecast,

one should be able to predict whether major events with current speeds above given limits say 50 cms^{-1} may occur over the next few days. Estimates of how the currents adapt to the topography may be produced. Forecast reliability will be best for the first 24 hours and will gradually decrease after that. Predictions a week or more ahead should probably be based on the general statistics, mean and variance of currents, for the area.

Such a system will be able to capture the dominating forcing during the pre-conditioning phase of major events. However, in the run-up phase, we

get a superposition of waves on a range of scales down to the scale of the local topography and the bottom boundary layer. The maximum velocities at a given locality will depend on how these waves interact at that particular point in space and time. We can not expect to forecast these interactions exactly. The system should be used as a tool to predict whether extreme events are likely to occur.

A further improvement would be to establish a real time monitoring system based on a numerical ocean model with focus on OL, and assimilation of atmospheric forcing and observations from the moorings. With such a system one should be able to give more realistic predictions of the state of the ocean around OL a few days ahead. However, to capture each front and each wave as they hit the slope, will require at least that we have exact knowledge about the boundary conditions. That is: an extremely dense array of moorings around OL as discussed above. In addition a model for OL resolving major length scales is required.

Figure 4. Observational network for Ormen Lange.

4 On the need for further work

To the developers of OL it may be important to have:

- a trustworthy prediction system for currents,
- statistics of currents profiles at different locations including frequencies, means and extreme values,
- information on how current profiles are related to atmospheric and internal pressure.

Advice on these issues should be based on best possible insight in the dynamics at OL. In this area processes on length scales from more than 100km down to a few meters and periods from days to seconds are important. The description given above of how the oceanic system at OL works and the suggested observing system, is based on the insight we have today. However, the number of processes important for the dynamics is very large and the nonlinear interactions between phenomena on this wide range of scales are strong. There are thus a number of issues that should be addressed more thoroughly to improve the quality of our advice and our results. Some of these are summarised below.

4.1 Effects of bottom topography

Fluid flow at OL is strongly directed along the general topography. This steering is stronger in areas where the slope is steeper. Local small sea-mounts, canyons, large boulders etc. will locally steer the flow. Such smaller scale features will also create drag on the general flow.

The flow close to the seabed is affected by the bottom roughness which may vary from one area to the next. Bed layer theory is well developed, see for instance Soulsby (1983). In ocean models the effects of the bed stress enters through a bottom roughness parameter, z_0 , which often is chosen to be 0.01, see Weatherly and Martin (1978) and Blumberg and Mellor (1987). Near bed flow depends on z_0 and with better knowledge about the character of the seabed, a better representation of this layer is possible. However, the models we have seem to be able to capture this logarithmic layer, that extends to a height of a few meters, fairly well. Producing space dependent values of z_0 may be important if the focus is on details in this layer. If the focus is more generally on major current events, there are other mechanisms that are believed to be more important.

4.1.1 Effects of the large scale topography

Based on principles of statistical mechanics and a maximum entropy principle, Holloway (1992) suggested a new method for estimating equilibrium

horizontal transports along larger scale topography. Gradients in the topography steer the background transports. Viscous terms in the models may be used to drag model transports towards this background transport rather than towards zero velocity which is used in most model studies today, including all studies for the Norwegian Sea that we are aware of. For a discussion of this parametrisation see Haidvogel and Beckmann (1999). Holloway argue that the effects of the new parametrisation will be most noticeable for coarse grid resolution studies. As we start to resolve the shelf and phenomena on the scale of the internal Rossby radius, the importance of including this effect will be reduced. To resolve processes at this scale, approximately 5 to 10km, requires a grid size of approximately 1km and with todays computers it is not possible to run a model covering the whole Norwegian Sea with this grid size. In experiments over a few days a grid size of 4km in Norwegian Sea models is approximately what we today can afford on our supercomputers, and for experiments over months and years 20km is still more realistic.

Alvarez et al. (1994) studied effects of topographic stress on the circulation in the Mediterranean using Holloway's parametrisation. In their model studies with grid size about 20km, the circulation became much more topographically steered with this parametrisation, and they claim that this is in better agreement with observations.

Many of our studies for OL have been with grid size 20km. The flow in these studies is generally following the topography, but according to Holloway this steering will be too weak. Results from this model have been used to drive model studies with grid sizes down to 200m. The quality of the results from these models, covering only small fractions of the Norwegian Sea, is strongly governed by the quality of the boundary conditions from the coarser grid model. Too weak topographic steering in the coarse grid model will give inadequate topographic steering in the fine grid models.

This is a fairly recent technique and there may be unwanted side effects, some of these are discussed by Holloway, that may require modifications. Nevertheless, topographic steering is very important. With the topographies available for the whole Norwegian Sea basin and for the OL area, experiments with the Holloway parametrisation may be performed and to include this effect will probably improve the quality of our model outputs considerably.

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: High.

Likelihood of success: Relatively high.

Difficulty: Underlying theory very difficult. Easy to implement in computer codes.

Work requirements: From a few months to many years of work depending on

how deep into the theory one wishes to go, and on how many experiments that are to be performed.

4.1.2 Effects of small scale topography

Topographic features on a scale smaller than ocean basin scale, but still large enough to be represented with the grid size we can afford today, may influence currents and waves considerably. This is for instance studied by Xing and Davies (1999). They focus on the shelf edge region off the west coast of Scotland where internal waves are strongly driven by the tide. It is shown that replacing a smooth topography with a recent and detailed topography may have important effects on the computed flow.

In several of the papers for the dr.scient. degree Ommundsen (2000) and co-authors studied effects of varying shelf width. Strong topographic steering was shown and in the transition zones between wide and narrow shelves the current fields became highly complex and small scale eddies appeared. North of OL the shelf width and slope changes and this curvature of the shelf will influence the currents also upstream at OL.

Effects of topographical features at these scales are clearly seen in the numerical studies already performed for OL, see Eliassen and Berntsen (2000) and Eliassen et al. (2000). Laboratory experiments, with rotating laboratory basins, may also be used to investigate topographic effects. This has for instance been done by Løvås et al. (2001). Some of the theory on current flow over irregular sea beds is recently summarised by Mathiesen (2001). To investigate these effects further both numerical and laboratory experiments should be set up for test cases having parameters relevant for OL and results from the two sets of experiments should be compared.

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: High.

Likelihood of success: Relatively high.

Difficulty: Relatively easy to set up the numerical experiments. The laboratory experiments require a rotating table and qualified persons.

Work requirements: From a few months to many years of work depending on how many experiments that are to be performed.

4.1.3 Parametrisation of drag from sub-grid scale topography

Topography with length scales smaller than those considered by Holloway (1992) and smaller than those that may be represented on the chosen model grid will steer the flow locally and create drag on the general along slope flow. For the OL area detailed maps with resolution down to one meter show a very rough topography with a number of sea-mounts, crests and troughs with length scales from a few meters to maybe 100m. Based on this detailed topography preliminary studies of how the general flow adjusts to the topography have been performed, see Avlesen and Berntsen (2001).

This study, with 4m horizontal grid size, show that the drag exerted on the general flow by this local roughness of the topography may be at least as important as the bottom drag. In model studies covering larger parts of OL, the resolution is typically from 200m to 20km and in such studies this topography drag effect is not accounted for in todays ocean models. However, in the recent book by Kantha and Clayson (2000) there is a section on atmospheric boundary layers and flow over local topography. Suggestions on how drag on the general flow may be computed are given.

The following approach to include effects of local scale topography in larger scale model studies may be suggested:

- i) From the atmospheric theory suggest one or more parametrisations of drag from local topography. Such parametrisations typically involves drag coefficients and parameters that must be determined.
- ii) From detailed maps of the OL area topography perform fine scale experiments where the topographical features are resolved and compute drag and energy losses.
- iii) Perform experiments for the same area with a strongly smoothed topography, much coarser horizontal resolution and the suggested parametrisations of topographical drag.
- iv) Compare results from the two sets of experiments above to compute drag coefficients and other parameters involved such that integrated drag and energy losses become similar.

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: High.

Likelihood of success: Fairly high.

Difficulty: Underlying theory very difficult. Easy to implement in computer codes.

Work requirements: From a few months to many years of work depending on how deep into the theory one wishes to go, and on how many experiments that are to be performed.

4.2 Nested model systems

To study the flow locally at OL with numerical models the approach has been to:

- i) Run a coarse grid size model covering the Norwegian Sea to compute initial and boundary conditions for
- ii) a fine grid size model covering OL.

Typically, both in our OL activity and in numerical oceanography in general, this is done with one way nesting. That is: No feed back from the fine grid model to the coarse grid model.

If the difference in resolution from the fine to the coarse grid is large, and the fine grid model only covers a small fraction of the ocean, the quality of the results from the fine grid model becomes strongly limited by the resolution of the coarse grid model. To improve this one may attempt to feed information from the fine grid model back to the coarse grid model continuously in coupled two ways nested model studies. This is for instance done by Heggelund and Berntsen (2000).

Two way nesting of fully 3-D baroclinic ocean models requires extremely precise coding, the chances of failure are large, and involves high computational costs. At present it is only done by very few groups in ocean modelling, see the introduction in Heggelund and Berntsen (2000) or Spall and Holland (1991); Fox and Maskell (1995, 1996); Blayo and Debreu (1999); Rowley and Ginis (1999). A scaling factor in the range from 1:2 to 1:5 is suggested. Two way nesting seem generally to improve the quality of the results on the fine grid, but also in this case the coarse grid resolution limits the quality of the fine grid results.

At OL waves and phenomena at scales larger than 100km down to a few meters interact. To model this a model system that on the coarsest scale resolves the major features and then gradually takes us down towards one meter with a scaling factor of at most 1:5. So far we have nested from 20km to 400m using a scaling factor of 1:50. To improve on this a practical approach is to start with a model covering most of the Norwegian Sea with 4km resolution followed by a one way nesting first to a 800m model and then down to a 160m grid size model focusing on OL. The Norwegian Sea 4km model is already under development by Thiem et al. (2001).

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: Moderate.

Likelihood of success: High for one level of nesting. Smaller for a multi level system.

Difficulty: Requires precise coding and experienced modellers.

Work requirements: For each level of nesting, coding, testing and experiments have to be performed. This requires at least one half year per level of nesting.

4.3 Run-ups and internal waves

Time series of temperature and velocities taken at Ormen Lange indicate that maxima in the velocities near the bottom and at larger depths, 500-1000m, off the shelf are associated with rapid changes in temperature. In some of these events there are changes in temperature of approximately 6 degrees Celsius over less than 24 hours. Such temperature changes may be translated using the climatology on hydrography from this area to vertical movements of water masses of approximately 5-600m. These vertical movements occur at the interface between Atlantic water and the colder intermediate Norwegian Sea water. The maxima in the velocities may be connected to propagation of internal waves or run ups of deeper water along the bottom of the shelf slope.

The literature on internal waves on shelf slopes is large and still growing. Observations, theoretical analysis, physical experiments and numerical experiments are used to get insight into these phenomena.

4.3.1 Parameters of relevance for Ormen Lange

The parameters of relevance for internal waves at Ormen Lange are the Coriolis parameter, f , the stratification, $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z}$, and the slope factor, γ . At our latitude f is approximately $1.3 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$. From the diagnostic climatology given in Engedahl et al. (1998) we find that density changes approximately with 0.5 kg m^{-3} from 250m to 900m depth giving $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z}$ in the range 0.0005 to 0.001 kg m^{-4} . This gives a buoyancy frequency, $N = \left(-\frac{g}{\rho_0} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z}\right)^{1/2}$, in the range $0.002-0.003 \text{ s}^{-1}$. From contour plots of the topography we find that the depth increases from 200m to 1000m over approximately 60km indicating a slope factor of 0.013. However, the topography at Ormen Lange is very rough and locally the slope factors may exceed 0.1, see for instance cross sections given in Eliassen and Berntsen (2000). Table 1 summarises the parameters of relevance.

Parameter	Value	Description
f	$\sim 1.3 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$	Coriolis parameter
$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z}$	$\sim 0.0005 - 0.001 \text{ kg m}^{-4}$	Stratification
N	$\sim 0.002 - 0.003 s^{-1}$	Buoyancy frequency
γ	$\sim 0.005 - 0.2$	Range slope factor
γ	$\sim 0.01 - 0.02$	Typical values slope factor

4.3.2 Review of some theory

The propagation of internal waves up a slope is discussed by Wunsch (1968). The appropriate equations to describe the motion are

$$\rho_0 u_t = -p'_x \quad (1)$$

$$\rho_0 w_t = -p'_z - g\rho' \quad (2)$$

$$\rho'_t + w\rho_{0z} = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$u_x + w_z = 0 \quad (4)$$

The model is for two-dimensional motion in a stably stratified Boussinesq fluid and for the non-rotating case. No viscosity is assumed. The horizontal velocity out from the slope is u and the vertical upward velocity is w . ρ_0 is the mean, stable density field and ρ' and p' are the perturbation density and pressure fields. Introducing a stream function, $\hat{\psi}$, from $u = -\hat{\psi}_z$ and $w = \hat{\psi}_x$ Wunsch (1968) obtain

$$\nabla^2 \hat{\psi}_{tt} + N^2 \hat{\psi}_{xx} = 0. \quad (5)$$

Then a modal solution is assumed such that

$$\hat{\psi} = \psi e^{-i\sigma t}. \quad (6)$$

The equation for ψ then becomes

$$\psi_{zz} - \frac{1}{c^2} \psi_{xx} = 0, \quad (7)$$

for $c^2 = \frac{\sigma^2}{N^2 - \sigma^2}$. For $c^2 > 0$ this equation is hyperbolic with the characteristics along the lines $cx \pm z = \text{constant}$. Wunsch (1968) considered a periodic internal wave propagating from the deep ocean onto a beach with constant slope γ and achieved after considerable algebra analytic solutions for this case.

There are three interesting cases:

- i) $\gamma < c$ or the subcritical case.

- ii) $\gamma = c$. In this case the characteristic $cx + z$ follow the bottom slope.
- iii) $\gamma > c$ or the supercritical case.

For the subcritical case the solutions show strong intensification of currents and waves along the bottom of the slope which again may induce strong oscillations in the temperature field. As the waves approach the bottom steepening of the crests and shortening of the wavelengths occur.

The solution is singular in the supercritical case due to the inviscid assumption. Wunsch (1968) stated: "... the slope itself is a region of high shear, which increases as the slope angle approaches the critical angle. Whether this leads to scouring of slopes, or strong mixing processes in the ocean is the subject of some conjecture."

Assuming waves forced by diurnal tides or inertial oscillations with period approximately 12 hours σ becomes approximately $1.45 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$ and $N^2 \gg \sigma^2$ at Ormen Lange and the hyperbolic wave solution for this frequency becomes possible. For these values we get c in the range 0.04 to 0.07. Thus for oscillations at this period $c > \gamma$ for most of the shelf slope at Ormen Lange and we may have strong intensification near the bottom. There are also locally areas where we have $c \sim \gamma$ giving extremely strong intensification along the bottom.

For oscillations with 24 hours period the values of c are approximately halved and we may get into the supercritical case in a larger area of Ormen Lange.

If we require $c = \gamma = 0.013$ and solve for the period, we find that periods in the range from 44 to 68 hours may create waves that hit the slope at the critical angle.

For periods in the range discussed for Ormen Lange above effects of the earths rotation should be considered, and Wunsch (1969) followed up his previous work by considering the viscous boundary layer, the earths rotation and three-dimensional effects.

For the two-dimensional inviscid case with rotation we get

$$c^2 = \frac{\sigma^2 - f^2}{N^2 - \sigma^2}. \quad (8)$$

The solution is otherwise changed. To achieve a wave solution in the rotating case we must therefore have $\sigma > f$, or the period of the wave must be shorter than the inertial period.

If we solve for $c = \gamma = 0.013$, we find periods slightly less than the inertial period may create waves with characteristics along the bottom slope. For steeper slopes the period of the critical wave gets shorter. For $\gamma = 0.1$

the period becomes 6.2 hours. For waves with this period and normal slope values, $\gamma \sim 0.013$, we have the subcritical case, but as the waves enter steeper bottom slopes the intensification may get significantly stronger.

For the supercritical case Wunsch (1969) showed that the introduction of an infinitesimal amount of friction cancel the singularity. For the supercritical case the energy flux is up-slope far from the bottom, but down slope near the bottom. This down slope energy flow may be traced back to the way waves reflect from the slope in the supercritical case.

Wunsch (1969) considered the three-dimensional inviscid case also. For this case a stream function is not available. From a Helmholtz equation for the vertical wave modes a complicated solution involving modified Bessel functions is achieved for the 3-D case. In the discussion it is stated: "The waves are reflected in the usual manner, turning parallel to the beach in shallow water."

Since the early papers by Wunsch the theory on breaking internal waves and their propagation up the slope has been further developed. Thorpe has for instance studied different aspects of the problem in a series of paper, see Thorpe (1999a,b, 2000, 2001). Internal waves may travel in groups of waves at the group velocity, Thorpe(1999b) and the occurrence of extreme values may related to group braking regions. Thorpe refers to relevant theory for surface waves by Trulsen (1989) which should be followed up also for internal waves.

4.3.3 Laboratory experiments

In Cacchione and Wunsch (1974) internal waves over a slope are studied in laboratory experiments. In agreement with linear theory, energy accumulate near the sea bottom with best agreement for the higher frequency waves. The lower frequency waves break much less violently than higher frequency waves. A bore is a high steep-fronted wave moving up a narrow estuary, caused by the tide. Cacchione and Wunsch (1974) show observations of distinctive bore-like features propagating upslope similar to swash and backwash associated with breaking of surface waves on the beach in the subcritical low-frequency case. For the subcritical case they find in general a good agreement with inviscid linear theory.

For the critical case a striking instability of the bottom layer is observed and the waves are heavily damped. For the supercritical case the waves are inhomogeneous and have a complex spatial dependency. The breakdown of linear theory for the critical and supercritical cases is expected since nonlinear effects will play a role and in the supercritical case the flow downwards along the bottom will produce unstable water-masses and almost immediate

vertical mixing not accounted for in the theory.

The laboratory experiments of Cacchione and Wunsch were for the case with linear stratification or constant buoyancy frequency. For Ormen Lange it may be more relevant to study waves at the interface between two water masses with different densities. This is being done at the Department of Mathematics, University of Oslo, under the leadership of Professor John Grue. The parameters and initial values for these experiments were chosen after a meeting between Grue, Berntsen and Furnes in the summer 2001.

4.3.4 Some early observations of internal waves

Mork (1972) considered oceanic responses to atmospheric forces. He referred to observations of vertical displacements of the density surfaces of 300m in connection with passages of low pressure systems at Ocean Weather Station M. These observations were not in agreement with dominating theories at that time. For the constant depth case, Mork put forward a theory for the vertical density displacement. Qualitative agreement was found, but the observed amplitudes could be 50 times greater than those predicted by the model. Mork pointed at the continental slope as an explanation for this discrepancy. Due to the slope free waves of periods larger than the inertial periods could also be supported. In the records a time lag of more than two days between the maximum displacement of density surfaces at a 2010m deep station and a 750m deep station is shown.

4.3.5 Suggested actions on internal waves

To be able to understand and predict extreme events, including extreme velocities, it is necessary to investigate further internal waves and their interactions at the shelf slope. The actions that should be taken may be grouped as follows:

- i) Studies and further developments of the theory,
- ii) Laboratory experiments,
- iii) Numerical experiments and
- iv) Observational programs.

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: High.

Likelihood of success: Relatively high.

Difficulty: Underlying theory very difficult. Some numerical studies may be performed relatively easily.

Work requirements: Each action above may easily require a person full time.

Generally if one may recruit persons with a good background for the job, contributions may be expected on a short time scale. To educate new staff with only a general background in the field to the level where they can deliver good results on internal wave studies may take much more time. With available qualified persons numerical and laboratory experiments may be performed within a few months of work.

4.4 Gravity currents

The water masses left atop of the continental shelf after a run-up event have higher density than the ambient environment. Hence a gravity current is likely to be generated when the water masses flow down the continental slope. Such flows may also be set up by sediment laden currents as well. For a review see Simpson (1987). These events are treated more thoroughly with focus on OL in a separate report Vikebø et al. (2001a), and only the main features will be repeated here.

There are two topics relevant to gravity currents at OL; Where will the gravity currents flow down the continental slope, the initial phase, and what velocities is expected as the currents plunge into the deep ocean?

The former requires a study of the local topography along the continental shelf. The water masses on the shelf will be transported along the shelf with the general flow and gravity currents will most likely be generated at troughs or depressions along the shelf edge.

The dynamics of gravity currents has been studied for several decades and is, if not fully, well understood. Simpson (1987) gives a nice review of the present status in the mid 80's. As a rule of thumb; the front of a gravity current from a steady origin down an incline moves with a speed proportional to the third root of the buoyancy flux at the source (Britter and Linden, 1980). Even though the gravitational force increases with inclination so does entrainment of ambient water. The upstream water masses entering the front moves with a velocity 60% higher. In other words, 40% of the main stream velocity causes mixing at the front.

Modelling of gravity currents ranges from simple numerical steady state stream tube models on an incline (Killworth, 1977; Alendal et al., 1994; Jungclaus et al., 1995) to full CFD simulations with topography (Jungclaus et al., 1995). The stream tube models were popular during the last decade because of their simplicity and low demand for computer power. They are usually one dimensional, in the along stream direction, and include influences from gravity, frictional, and rotational forces in addition to mixing due to

entrainment. It has been shown that the steady state assumption breaks down when the current speed approaches the phase velocity of waves on the current/ambient interface (Alendal et al., 1994; Alendal, 1995). Also for some flows it is necessary to include changes in stream tube height along the path and cross-stream variations (Borenäs and Wåhlin, 2000).

A gravity current will also be steered by bottom topography, an effect not present in the stream tube models. For instance, a gravity current flowing down a canyon will depending on time scale travel up on one side due to earth rotation. A temporal 3D model is required in order to include topographic effects. With the tools available, BOM (Berntsen, 2000) and MITgcm (Marshall et al., 1997b,a), it should be manageable to study a couple of scenarios where gravity currents flow down the continental slope on OL.

The picture is even more complex if sediments are suspended in the current. They will have an accelerating effect on the current due to increased density difference. To include this effect a proper settling/resuspension sub-model is required.

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: Medium.

Likelihood of success: Very high for stream tube modelling. High for CFD modelling.

Difficulty: Stream tube modeling easy, CFD modeling requires proper topographic treatment. Will benefit from the other activities related to topography.

Work requirements: Stream tube modeling: 2 months. CFD modeling 6 months to several years pending on required degree of accuracy and number of studies performed.

4.5 Risk of high current assessment by statistical methods.

Through the aforementioned activities and through the in-situ measurement program by the Ormen Lange consortium, a lot of data on current speed and direction will become available. By using a statistical method, frequently applied in studies on location and design of windmill power plants, a probability distribution on current speed can be built. This distribution can subsequently estimate probability, frequency and amplitude of high current events.

The method consist of fitting, through regression, the data with a current

speed distribution, often the Weibull or the log-Weibull distributions (Mann et al., 1974), by determining the unknown shape factors. Once a distribution is established it gives expected currents, and frequency and amplitude of rare events with high current speed that might jeopardise a pipeline.

Lun and Lam (2000) used the method for three different locations in Hong Kong using long term, thirty years, time series of hourly wind measurements. The three locations were used as a first step for establishing an adequate wind information data base for better predictions of wind related assessments.

Torres et al. (1999) describes a study on wind speed distribution and the most frequent wind directions for planning and designing of wind mill power plants. According to their paper and references therein the Weibull distribution has shown to give the best fit with wind speed data. One of their conclusions is that a power station situated in a wide channel show a clear dominant wind direction, as oppose to a plant in mountainous areas. Their approach might be useful for our studies on topographic steering and current fluctuations at OL.

Another study by Huang et al. (2001) evaluate long-term hurricane risk assessment in the southern United States. They develop a probabilistic hurricane event model with parameters derived from statistical analysis of storms including radius of maximum winds, central pressure difference, landfall location, storm track, and decay rate. Another interesting report published on the world wide web

(<http://www.oas.org/EN/cdmp/document/kma/coastal/coastrep.htm>) produce hurricane return period maps for the Caribbean. Based on our present understanding on the driving mechanisms at OL, the passage of storms, their extent, pressure gradient and track, a similar study would be interesting for ocean currents at OL.

Another benefit from such an exercise, by analysing both in-situ and numerical data in the same manner, a new comparison tool becomes available. In-situ data are usually time series of point measurements while numerical simulation data has spatial extent in addition to the temporal. It will be a valuable tool for model validation to have a statistical algorithm to see differences between the two classes of data sets in order to check consistency of the models.

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: High. Might introduce new methods for analysing model results and comparison

Likelihood of success: Medium to high pending on how deep into the material we go.

Work requirements: One year for establishing the framework and analysing

a selection of data sets. Once established new data sets can be analysed as they become available.

4.6 Correlations in neighbouring time series

Time series of currents and hydrography (temperature and salinity) at different locations at OL are essential to establish statistics on currents. The time series show, however, often erratic behaviour and it is often difficult to comprehend the events seen. In Vikebø et al. (2001a) the focus has been on three events giving peak values in the near bottom velocities. The events are related to travelling atmospheric low pressure systems, but there are also events that are not clearly coupled to the atmospheric pressure. Studying the time series of for instance velocities at different localities at OL, it is difficult to see any systematic time lags or correlations between neighbouring localities. However, systematic computations of the cross-correlation functions, see Emery and Thomson (1997), between different stations have not been performed so far. There are also measurements programs, overlapping in time with the time series at OL, for the Svinøy section close to the OL area in the southward direction, see Orvik et al. (2001). Comparisons and cross-correlations of Svinøy section and OL time series may contribute to the understanding of how waves and water masses are propagated along the shelf slope, and will be important when designing monitoring and forecasting systems. In particular possible correlations between the major events seen in neighbouring time series will be important.

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: Uncertain, depends on the outcome of the study.

Likelihood of success: Relatively high.

Difficulty: In principle fairly straightforward.

Work requirements: To work with these time series and to analyse them may be very time consuming. Each time series for a given position and depth should be related to all the others for that period for different depths at the same horizontal position and to time series at different depths at neighbouring positions. The time series should also be related to time series for the forcing. That is at least time series for wind or atmospheric pressure.

4.7 Maps of U-mean and U-max as function of Grad-P

Products that may be useful to the developers of OL would possibly be maps of expected values of current speeds, U_{mean} , and maps of expected extreme values of current speeds, U_{max} , as functions of lateral position and depth above sea bed. That is: For each lateral position vertical profiles of U_{mean} and U_{max} . Preliminary maps of this kind may be produced using existing time series and the insight gained from model studies. Such maps may be used as a priori estimates of U_{mean} and U_{max} when there are no further knowledge about the forcing of the system. The estimates of U_{mean} will probably be relatively good. However, to developers of the gas field the quality of the estimates of U_{max} may be more important. At present these estimates will be based on observations containing relatively few extreme events. The observations are filtered in time, and they are too sparse in space to capture all relevant spatial scales. Thus, estimates of U_{max} will probably be very uncertain.

Longer time series at several positions, preferably with better time resolution, may be used to improve the quality of the Weibull statistics and thus the estimates of U_{max} . Also repeated model experiments where the forcing is chosen from distributions of atmospheric and internal pressure may be used to produce statistics about U_{mean} and U_{max} .

In reality velocities and their maxima are strongly related to the gradients in the pressure as discussed above. Thus with more precise information about atmospheric and internal pressure which we may have in forecasts for a few days, also more precise estimates of U_{mean} and U_{max} for the next few days may be produced. These statistics may be produced for instance through repeated model simulations where the strength of forcing is given, but the specific pathway of the pressure disturbance chosen randomly.

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: Probably low.

Likelihood of success: Relatively high.

Difficulty: In principle fairly straightforward.

Work requirements: It will be time consuming to produce the maps and to make them easily accessible to the users.

5 Conclusions

Activities on a wide range of scientific issues and related tasks, involving a large group of people, are thus possible to improve the present understanding

of currents and current profiles at OL. Some activities may involve laboratory experiments and require physical models, for some studies also rotating tables, and such experiments may be performed by competent research groups in Oslo and/or Trondheim. Other activities involve analysis of measured time series. Such analysis may be performed by the present research group, but should preferably be done by oceanographers that are more familiar with analysing field data.

The present research group may perform relevant model studies on a range of spatial scales. Problem areas that may be addressed include:

- a) Topographical steering (Holloway, 1992),
- b) Parametrisation of drag from sub-grid scale topographical features,
- c) Further model nesting with focus on OL,
- d) Idealised studies of internal waves/run-ups,
- e) Studies of gravity currents with realistic topography,
- f) Establishing necessary statistics to produce U_{mean} and U_{max} ,
- g) Maps of current profiles of U_{mean} and U_{max} .

Further activities on the topics above will be relevant to OL, and they may contribute to the basic understanding of physical processes outside the shelf break.

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1 Introduction

The exploration of hydrocarbons have in recent years been directed more and more towards deep water beyond the continental margins. This involves new challenges as the environmental forces on e.g. moorings and risers will, to a greater extent, be dominated by the currents.

The currents at the shelf edge and along the continental slopes are generally subjected to a wide range of dynamical activities. This is due to the fact that such a pronounced change in bottom topography acts as a converter for on-off shelf exchange processes. It is also an efficient trap for a number of wave phenomena. As an example, tides are generated in the deep oceans and propagate towards the shelf zones. As the tidal wave progress over the shelf slope it is gradually converted from weaker currents to stronger currents. Under favourable conditions this is accompanied by formation of internal waves that under given conditions can disintegrate into solitary waves. See Siedler et al. (2001) for a description of the general ocean circulation and Huthnance (1992, 1995) for further descriptions of shelf edge and shelf slope phenomena.

It has been a general opinion that currents in the deep oceans are fairly weak. However, so far the focus has been more on general flow and mean transports rather than on peak events in oceanography. This has also been the case for WOCE (World Ocean Circulation Experiment) Siedler et al. (2001). For the time and space mean circulation, the velocities are generally small, less than a few cm s^{-1} , in the deep ocean.

To this standard picture of large gyres in each of the ocean basins, pictures of patchy mixing processes, topographically steered jets and variability are, however, emerging. See the chapter on the interior circulation of the ocean in Siedler et al. (2001). In Hansen and Østerhus (2000) velocities larger than 100 cm s^{-1} through the Faroe bank Channel are reported. The time series from the offshore gas field Ormen Lange (OL) located in the Storegga region off mid-Norway at water depths from approximately 800m to 1100m, see Figure 1, also show that the velocities during peak events may exceed 50 cm s^{-1} , see Mathisen (2001) and Eliassen et al. (2000). Often rapid changes in the flow are seen, and since the recorded velocities are time filtered, the true maximum velocities may be underestimated at present. The observational networks have so far not been dense enough to resolve all important length scales, and there are large geographical variations in the flow. There may, therefore, be areas where we get intensification and speeds exceeding 100 cm s^{-1} also at OL. Such flows may create strong drags on risers, pipelines or mooring lines that may be of concern for offshore operations and development.

Since 1999 our research groups at the Mathematics Department, Univer-

sity of Bergen, and the Nansen Center have in cooperation with Norsk Hydro tried to understand currents and waves at OL. The approach has been to:

- a) Study relevant theory and papers for the Norwegian Sea and specially those parts dealing with the shelf edge and shelf slope off mid-Norway.
- b) Study general theory for shelf edge and shelf slope processes.
- c) Apply numerical models to estimate the currents and current profiles at OL.
- d) Apply numerical models to understand the underlying processes and their impact on the currents.
- e) Analyse available time series of currents and hydrography from OL.

The objectives of the studies have been to improve the understanding of off shelf current systems and subsequently use this knowledge as support for offshore operations and construction of design current profiles. We have used the Ormen Lange/Storegga area as a study site. Access to time series of currents and temperature at OL and to long time series at the Svinøy section (Orvik et al., 2001), through cooperation with the Geophysics Department, UiB, has been very important.

The results so far have been published in a series of technical reports (Eliassen and Berntsen, 2000; Eliassen et al., 2000; Heggelund and Berntsen, 2000, 2001). The ocean model applied in these studies has been described in Berntsen (2000). More recently a non-hydrostatic ocean model developed at MIT has been applied to study flow around local topography at OL Marshall et al. (1997b,a). At present work on a number of manuscripts describing on-going activity and results are in progress, Vikebø et al. (2001a,c,b); Avlesen and Berntsen (2001); Sørflaten and Berntsen (2001); Thiem et al. (2001). There is also on-going activities at the Geophysics Department (Orvik, Skagseth and Østerhus) on analysing time series of currents and hydrography from OL and the surrounding ocean.

In the present report we will try to summarise what we today regard as the major forcing mechanisms. We will discuss their effects on the flow and waves. Based on the present understanding of how the oceanic system at OL works, a possible monitoring system that may be used to predict major events a few days ahead will be described. A discussion of areas where further research and developments are needed to improve our understanding of the mechanisms behind events with large velocities and to design a possible monitoring system will be given.

Ormen Lange is used as a study area in our activities, but the methods may be applied to any sea region given that the topography and necessary input data are available.

during storms and/or approaching internal density fronts. Figure 2 describes the water masses along the shelf off mid-Norway. During such events the density surfaces tend to undershoot their equilibrium level, and as the forcing weakens, the suppressed water may run up along the shelf slope. In this run up phase peak values in the velocities are often found. During run up colder and heavier water masses are lifted up on the shelf. As the wave off shelf retreats some of this heavy water on shelf may be separated from the water mass it originated from. This heavy on shelf water mass may follow the general flow along the shelf and, later on, flow down cross shelf canyons and create gravity currents. After front passages the oscillations of these density surfaces may continue for days, but their amplitudes will gradually decrease. A cartoon of these processes is given in Figure 3.

Figure 2: The water masses in the region divided into four different layers; Norwegian Coastal Water (NCW), Atlantic Water (AW), Norwegian Sea Arctic Intermediate Water (NSAIW) and Norwegian Sea Deep Water (NSDW).

Figure 3: A plausible model explaining the events occurring in the time series from Ormen Lange. The model is divided into three different phases; pre-conditioning, 'run-ups' and gravity currents.

3 Prediction of currents and waves

Gradients in the pressure create acceleration of water masses. This is essential in the Reynolds averaged momentum equations, and in agreement with our model experiments and analysis of measurements so far.

To be able to predict major events in velocities at OL, one must therefore predict peaks in pressure gradients.

Forecasts of atmospheric low pressure are routinely produced and these are trustworthy up to at maximum one week ahead.

There are major events that apparently are not linked to atmospheric pressure gradients, at least not on a short time scale. To predict internal pressure gradients in the ocean, one must have an array of current meter and hydrographic moorings surrounding OL. Assuming that the internal pressure fronts are propagated with the speed of the water masses, approximately 20 cms^{-1} , they move approximately 50 to 100 km over 5 days. Along such fronts there will be eddies and filaments. A typical length scale of these phenomena will be the internal Rossby radius which is 5 to 10 km in our area. To capture each internal eddy and filament propagating towards OL accurately will require an array of moorings along the circle around OL with radius 100km and a distance of approximately 1km between each mooring. That is more than 600 moorings. This is probably not feasible. However, by having a few moorings upstream in the general flow direction, south/south-west, one may be able to capture major fronts moving towards OL without capturing the details on the front. In addition with a hydrographic station 100km upstream from OL on the shelf, one may be able to detect possible cores of dense and cold water flowing towards OL that may create dangerous downslope gravity currents.

Thus with an observing system including:

- a) atmospheric weather forecasts,
- b) an array of 4 to 5 current and hydrographic moorings on a circle with radius $\sim 100\text{km}$ around OL reporting in real time,
- c) online ocean weather forecast,

one should be able to predict whether major events with current speeds above given limits say 50 cms^{-1} may occur over the next few days. Estimates of how the currents adapt to the topography may be produced. Forecast reliability will be best for the first 24 hours and will gradually decrease after that. Predictions a week or more ahead should probably be based on the general statistics, mean and variance of currents, for the area.

Such a system will be able to capture the dominating forcing during the pre-conditioning phase of major events. However, in the run-up phase, we

- a trustworthy prediction system for currents,
- statistics of currents profiles at different locations including frequencies, means and extreme values,
- information on how current profiles are related to atmospheric and internal pressure.

Advice on these issues should be based on best possible insight in the dynamics at OL. In this area processes on length scales from more than 100km down to a few meters and periods from days to seconds are important. The description given above of how the oceanic system at OL works and the suggested observing system, is based on the insight we have today. However, the number of processes important for the dynamics is very large and the nonlinear interactions between phenomena on this wide range of scales are strong. There are thus a number of issues that should be addressed more thoroughly to improve the quality of our advice and our results. Some of these are summarised below.

4.1 Effects of bottom topography

Fluid flow at OL is strongly directed along the general topography. This steering is stronger in areas where the slope is steeper. Local small sea-mounts, canyons, large boulders etc. will locally steer the flow. Such smaller scale features will also create drag on the general flow.

The flow close to the seabed is affected by the bottom roughness which may vary from one area to the next. Bed layer theory is well developed, see for instance Soulsby (1983). In ocean models the effects of the bed stress enters through a bottom roughness parameter, z_0 , which often is chosen to be 0.01, see Weatherly and Martin (1978) and Blumberg and Mellor (1987). Near bed flow depends on z_0 and with better knowledge about the character of the seabed, a better representation of this layer is possible. However, the models we have seem to be able to capture this logarithmic layer, that extends to a height of a few meters, fairly well. Producing space dependent values of z_0 may be important if the focus is on details in this layer. If the focus is more generally on major current events, there are other mechanisms that are believed to be more important.

4.1.1 Effects of the large scale topography

Based on principles of statistical mechanics and a maximum entropy principle, Holloway (1992) suggested a new method for estimating equilibrium

horizontal transports along larger scale topography. Gradients in the topography steer the background transports. Viscous terms in the models may be used to drag model transports towards this background transport rather than towards zero velocity which is used in most model studies today, including all studies for the Norwegian Sea that we are aware of. For a discussion of this parametrisation see Haidvogel and Beckmann (1999). Holloway argue that the effects of the new parametrisation will be most noticeable for coarse grid resolution studies. As we start to resolve the shelf and phenomena on the scale of the internal Rossby radius, the importance of including this effect will be reduced. To resolve processes at this scale, approximately 5 to 10km, requires a grid size of approximately 1km and with todays computers it is not possible to run a model covering the whole Norwegian Sea with this grid size. In experiments over a few days a grid size of 4km in Norwegian Sea models is approximately what we today can afford on our supercomputers, and for experiments over months and years 20km is still more realistic.

Alvarez et al. (1994) studied effects of topographic stress on the circulation in the Mediterranean using Holloway's parametrisation. In their model studies with grid size about 20km, the circulation became much more topographically steered with this parametrisation, and they claim that this is in better agreement with observations.

Many of our studies for OL have been with grid size 20km. The flow in these studies is generally following the topography, but according to Holloway this steering will be too weak. Results from this model have been used to drive model studies with grid sizes down to 200m. The quality of the results from these models, covering only small fractions of the Norwegian Sea, is strongly governed by the quality of the boundary conditions from the coarser grid model. Too weak topographic steering in the coarse grid model will give inadequate topographic steering in the fine grid models.

This is a fairly recent technique and there may be unwanted side effects, some of these are discussed by Holloway, that may require modifications. Nevertheless, topographic steering is very important. With the topographies available for the whole Norwegian Sea basin and for the OL area, experiments with the Holloway parametrisation may be performed and to include this effect will probably improve the quality of our model outputs considerably.

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: High.

Likelihood of success: Relatively high.

Difficulty: Underlying theory very difficult. Easy to implement in computer codes.

Work requirements: From a few months to many years of work depending on

how deep into the theory one wishes to go, and on how many experiments that are to be performed.

4.1.2 Effects of small scale topography

Topographic features on a scale smaller than ocean basin scale, but still large enough to be represented with the grid size we can afford today, may influence currents and waves considerably. This is for instance studied by Xing and Davies (1999). They focus on the shelf edge region off the west coast of Scotland where internal waves are strongly driven by the tide. It is shown that replacing a smooth topography with a recent and detailed topography may have important effects on the computed flow.

In several of the papers for the dr.scient. degree Ommundsen (2000) and co-authors studied effects of varying shelf width. Strong topographic steering was shown and in the transition zones between wide and narrow shelves the current fields became highly complex and small scale eddies appeared. North of OL the shelf width and slope changes and this curvature of the shelf will influence the currents also upstream at OL.

Effects of topographical features at these scales are clearly seen in the numerical studies already performed for OL, see Eliassen and Berntsen (2000) and Eliassen et al. (2000). Laboratory experiments, with rotating laboratory basins, may also be used to investigate topographic effects. This has for instance been done by Løvås et al. (2001). Some of the theory on current flow over irregular sea beds is recently summarised by Mathiesen (2001). To investigate these effects further both numerical and laboratory experiments should be set up for test cases having parameters relevant for OL and results from the two sets of experiments should be compared.

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: High.

Likelihood of success: Relatively high.

Difficulty: Relatively easy to set up the numerical experiments. The laboratory experiments require a rotating table and qualified persons.

Work requirements: From a few months to many years of work depending on how many experiments that are to be performed.

4.1.3 Parametrisation of drag from sub-grid scale topography

Topography with length scales smaller than those considered by Holloway (1992) and smaller than those that may be represented on the chosen model grid will steer the flow locally and create drag on the general along slope flow. For the OL area detailed maps with resolution down to one meter show a very rough topography with a number of sea-mounts, crests and troughs with length scales from a few meters to maybe 100m. Based on this detailed topography preliminary studies of how the general flow adjusts to the topography have been performed, see Avlesen and Berntsen (2001).

This study, with 4m horizontal grid size, show that the drag exerted on the general flow by this local roughness of the topography may be at least as important as the bottom drag. In model studies covering larger parts of OL, the resolution is typically from 200m to 20km and in such studies this topography drag effect is not accounted for in todays ocean models. However, in the recent book by Kantha and Clayson (2000) there is a section on atmospheric boundary layers and flow over local topography. Suggestions on how drag on the general flow may be computed are given.

The following approach to include effects of local scale topography in larger scale model studies may be suggested:

- i) From the atmospheric theory suggest one or more parametrisations of drag from local topography. Such parametrisations typically involves drag coefficients and parameters that must be determined.
- ii) From detailed maps of the OL area topography perform fine scale experiments where the topographical features are resolved and compute drag and energy losses.
- iii) Perform experiments for the same area with a strongly smoothed topography, much coarser horizontal resolution and the suggested parametrisations of topographical drag.
- iv) Compare results from the two sets of experiments above to compute drag coefficients and other parameters involved such that integrated drag and energy losses become similar.

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: High.

Likelihood of success: Fairly high.

Difficulty: Underlying theory very difficult. Easy to implement in computer codes.

Work requirements: From a few months to many years of work depending on how deep into the theory one wishes to go, and on how many experiments that are to be performed.

4.2 Nested model systems

To study the flow locally at OL with numerical models the approach has been to:

- i) Run a coarse grid size model covering the Norwegian Sea to compute initial and boundary conditions for
- ii) a fine grid size model covering OL.

Typically, both in our OL activity and in numerical oceanography in general, this is done with one way nesting. That is: No feed back from the fine grid model to the coarse grid model.

If the difference in resolution from the fine to the coarse grid is large, and the fine grid model only covers a small fraction of the ocean, the quality of the results from the fine grid model becomes strongly limited by the resolution of the coarse grid model. To improve this one may attempt to feed information from the fine grid model back to the coarse grid model continuously in coupled two ways nested model studies. This is for instance done by Heggelund and Berntsen (2000).

Two way nesting of fully 3-D baroclinic ocean models requires extremely precise coding, the chances of failure are large, and involves high computational costs. At present it is only done by very few groups in ocean modelling, see the introduction in Heggelund and Berntsen (2000) or Spall and Holland (1991); Fox and Maskell (1995, 1996); Blayo and Debreu (1999); Rowley and Ginis (1999). A scaling factor in the range from 1:2 to 1:5 is suggested. Two way nesting seem generally to improve the quality of the results on the fine grid, but also in this case the coarse grid resolution limits the quality of the fine grid results.

At OL waves and phenomena at scales larger than 100km down to a few meters interact. To model this a model system that on the coarsest scale resolves the major features and then gradually takes us down towards one meter with a scaling factor of at most 1:5. So far we have nested from 20km to 400m using a scaling factor of 1:50. To improve on this a practical approach is to start with a model covering most of the Norwegian Sea with 4km resolution followed by a one way nesting first to a 800m model and then down to a 160m grid size model focusing on OL. The Norwegian Sea 4km model is already under development by Thiem et al. (2001).

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: Moderate.

Likelihood of success: High for one level of nesting. Smaller for a multi level system.

Difficulty: Requires precise coding and experienced modellers.

Work requirements: For each level of nesting, coding, testing and experiments have to be performed. This requires at least one half year per level of nesting.

4.3 Run-ups and internal waves

Time series of temperature and velocities taken at Ormen Lange indicate that maxima in the velocities near the bottom and at larger depths, 500-1000m, off the shelf are associated with rapid changes in temperature. In some of these events there are changes in temperature of approximately 6 degrees Celsius over less than 24 hours. Such temperature changes may be translated using the climatology on hydrography from this area to vertical movements of water masses of approximately 5-600m. These vertical movements occur at the interface between Atlantic water and the colder intermediate Norwegian Sea water. The maxima in the velocities may be connected to propagation of internal waves or run ups of deeper water along the bottom of the shelf slope.

The literature on internal waves on shelf slopes is large and still growing. Observations, theoretical analysis, physical experiments and numerical experiments are used to get insight into these phenomena.

4.3.1 Parameters of relevance for Ormen Lange

The parameters of relevance for internal waves at Ormen Lange are the Coriolis parameter, f , the stratification, $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z}$, and the slope factor, γ . At our latitude f is approximately $1.3 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$. From the diagnostic climatology given in Engedahl et al. (1998) we find that density changes approximately with 0.5 kg m^{-3} from 250m to 900m depth giving $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z}$ in the range 0.0005 to 0.001 kg m^{-4} . This gives a buoyancy frequency, $N = \left(-\frac{g}{\rho_0} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z}\right)^{1/2}$, in the range 0.002-0.003 s^{-1} . From contour plots of the topography we find that the depth increases from 200m to 1000m over approximately 60km indicating a slope factor of 0.013. However, the topography at Ormen Lange is very rough and locally the slope factors may exceed 0.1, see for instance cross sections given in Eliassen and Berntsen (2000). Table 1 summarises the parameters of relevance.

Parameter	Value	Description
f	$\sim 1.3 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$	Coriolis parameter
$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z}$	$\sim 0.0005 - 0.001 \text{ kg m}^{-4}$	Stratification
N	$\sim 0.002 - 0.003 s^{-1}$	Buoyancy frequency
γ	$\sim 0.005 - 0.2$	Range slope factor
γ	$\sim 0.01 - 0.02$	Typical values slope factor

4.3.2 Review of some theory

The propagation of internal waves up a slope is discussed by Wunsch (1968). The appropriate equations to describe the motion are

$$\rho_0 u_t = -p'_x \quad (1)$$

$$\rho_0 w_t = -p'_z - g\rho' \quad (2)$$

$$\rho'_t + w\rho_{0z} = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$u_x + w_z = 0 \quad (4)$$

The model is for two-dimensional motion in a stably stratified Boussinesq fluid and for the non-rotating case. No viscosity is assumed. The horizontal velocity out from the slope is u and the vertical upward velocity is w . ρ_0 is the mean, stable density field and ρ' and p' are the perturbation density and pressure fields. Introducing a stream function, $\hat{\psi}$, from $u = -\hat{\psi}_z$ and $w = \hat{\psi}_x$ Wunsch (1968) obtain

$$\nabla^2 \hat{\psi}_{tt} + N^2 \hat{\psi}_{xx} = 0. \quad (5)$$

Then a modal solution is assumed such that

$$\hat{\psi} = \psi e^{-i\sigma t}. \quad (6)$$

The equation for ψ then becomes

$$\psi_{zz} - \frac{1}{c^2} \psi_{xx} = 0, \quad (7)$$

for $c^2 = \frac{\sigma^2}{N^2 - \sigma^2}$. For $c^2 > 0$ this equation is hyperbolic with the characteristics along the lines $cx \pm z = \text{constant}$. Wunsch (1968) considered a periodic internal wave propagating from the deep ocean onto a beach with constant slope γ and achieved after considerable algebra analytic solutions for this case.

There are three interesting cases:

- i) $\gamma < c$ or the subcritical case.

ii) $\gamma = c$. In this case the characteristic $cx + z$ follow the bottom slope.

iii) $\gamma > c$ or the supercritical case.

For the subcritical case the solutions show strong intensification of currents and waves along the bottom of the slope which again may induce strong oscillations in the temperature field. As the waves approach the bottom steepening of the crests and shortening of the wavelengths occur.

The solution is singular in the supercritical case due to the inviscid assumption. Wunsch (1968) stated: "... the slope itself is a region of high shear, which increases as the slope angle approaches the critical angle. Whether this leads to scouring of slopes, or strong mixing processes in the ocean is the subject of some conjecture."

Assuming waves forced by diurnal tides or inertial oscillations with period approximately 12 hours σ becomes approximately $1.45 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$ and $N^2 \gg \sigma^2$ at Ormen Lange and the hyperbolic wave solution for this frequency becomes possible. For these values we get c in the range 0.04 to 0.07. Thus for oscillations at this period $c > \gamma$ for most of the shelf slope at Ormen Lange and we may have strong intensification near the bottom. There are also locally areas where we have $c \sim \gamma$ giving extremely strong intensification along the bottom.

For oscillations with 24 hours period the values of c are approximately halved and we may get into the supercritical case in a larger area of Ormen Lange.

If we require $c = \gamma = 0.013$ and solve for the period, we find that periods in the range from 44 to 68 hours may create waves that hit the slope at the critical angle.

For periods in the range discussed for Ormen Lange above effects of the earths rotation should be considered, and Wunsch (1969) followed up his previous work by considering the viscous boundary layer, the earths rotation and three-dimensional effects.

For the two-dimensional inviscid case with rotation we get

$$c^2 = \frac{\sigma^2 - f^2}{N^2 - \sigma^2}. \quad (8)$$

The solution is otherwise changed. To achieve a wave solution in the rotating case we must therefore have $\sigma > f$, or the period of the wave must be shorter than the inertial period.

If we solve for $c = \gamma = 0.013$, we find periods slightly less than the inertial period may create waves with characteristics along the bottom slope. For steeper slopes the period of the critical wave gets shorter. For $\gamma = 0.1$

the period becomes 6.2 hours. For waves with this period and normal slope values, $\gamma \sim 0.013$, we have the subcritical case, but as the waves enter steeper bottom slopes the intensification may get significantly stronger.

For the supercritical case Wunsch (1969) showed that the introduction of an infinitesimal amount of friction cancel the singularity. For the supercritical case the energy flux is up-slope far from the bottom, but down slope near the bottom. This down slope energy flow may be traced back to the way waves reflect from the slope in the supercritical case.

Wunsch (1969) considered the three-dimensional inviscid case also. For this case a stream function is not available. From a Helmholtz equation for the vertical wave modes a complicated solution involving modified Bessel functions is achieved for the 3-D case. In the discussion it is stated: "The waves are reflected in the usual manner, turning parallel to the beach in shallow water."

Since the early papers by Wunsch the theory on breaking internal waves and their propagation up the slope has been further developed. Thorpe has for instance studied different aspects of the problem in a series of paper, see Thorpe (1999a,b, 2000, 2001). Internal waves may travel in groups of waves at the group velocity, Thorpe(1999b) and the occurrence of extreme values may related to group braking regions. Thorpe refers to relevant theory for surface waves by Trulsen (1989) which should be followed up also for internal waves.

4.3.3 Laboratory experiments

In Cacchione and Wunsch (1974) internal waves over a slope are studied in laboratory experiments. In agreement with linear theory, energy accumulate near the sea bottom with best agreement for the higher frequency waves. The lower frequency waves break much less violently than higher frequency waves. A bore is a high steep-fronted wave moving up a narrow estuary, caused by the tide. Cacchione and Wunsch (1974) show observations of distinctive bore-like features propagating upslope similar to swash and backwash associated with breaking of surface waves on the beach in the subcritical low-frequency case. For the subcritical case they find in general a good agreement with inviscid linear theory.

For the critical case a striking instability of the bottom layer is observed and the waves are heavily damped. For the supercritical case the waves are inhomogeneous and have a complex spatial dependency. The breakdown of linear theory for the critical and supercritical cases is expected since nonlinear effects will play a role and in the supercritical case the flow downwards along the bottom will produce unstable water-masses and almost immediate

vertical mixing not accounted for in the theory.

The laboratory experiments of Cacchione and Wunsch were for the case with linear stratification or constant buoyancy frequency. For Ormen Lange it may be more relevant to study waves at the interface between two water masses with different densities. This is being done at the Department of Mathematics, University of Oslo, under the leadership of Professor John Grue. The parameters and initial values for these experiments were chosen after a meeting between Grue, Berntsen and Furnes in the summer 2001.

4.3.4 Some early observations of internal waves

Mork (1972) considered oceanic responses to atmospheric forces. He referred to observations of vertical displacements of the density surfaces of 300m in connection with passages of low pressure systems at Ocean Weather Station M. These observations were not in agreement with dominating theories at that time. For the constant depth case, Mork put forward a theory for the vertical density displacement. Qualitative agreement was found, but the observed amplitudes could be 50 times greater than those predicted by the model. Mork pointed at the continental slope as an explanation for this discrepancy. Due to the slope free waves of periods larger than the inertial periods could also be supported. In the records a time lag of more than two days between the maximum displacement of density surfaces at a 2010m deep station and a 750m deep station is shown.

4.3.5 Suggested actions on internal waves

To be able to understand and predict extreme events, including extreme velocities, it is necessary to investigate further internal waves and their interactions at the shelf slope. The actions that should be taken may be grouped as follows:

- i) Studies and further developments of the theory,
- ii) Laboratory experiments,
- iii) Numerical experiments and
- iv) Observational programs.

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: High.

Likelihood of success: Relatively high.

Difficulty: Underlying theory very difficult. Some numerical studies may be performed relatively easily.

Work requirements: Each action above may easily require a person full time.

Generally if one may recruit persons with a good background for the job, contributions may be expected on a short time scale. To educate new staff with only a general background in the field to the level where they can deliver good results on internal wave studies may take much more time. With available qualified persons numerical and laboratory experiments may be performed within a few months of work.

4.4 Gravity currents

The water masses left atop of the continental shelf after a run-up event have higher density than the ambient environment. Hence a gravity current is likely to be generated when the water masses flow down the continental slope. Such flows may also be set up by sediment laden currents as well. For a review see Simpson (1987). These events are treated more thoroughly with focus on OL in a separate report Vikebø et al. (2001a), and only the main features will be repeated here.

There are two topics relevant to gravity currents at OL; Where will the gravity currents flow down the continental slope, the initial phase, and what velocities is expected as the currents plunge into the deep ocean?

The former requires a study of the local topography along the continental shelf. The water masses on the shelf will be transported along the shelf with the general flow and gravity currents will most likely be generated at troughs or depressions along the shelf edge.

The dynamics of gravity currents has been studied for several decades and is, if not fully, well understood. Simpson (1987) gives a nice review of the present status in the mid 80's. As a rule of thumb; the front of a gravity current from a steady origin down an incline moves with a speed proportional to the third root of the buoyancy flux at the source (Britter and Linden, 1980). Even though the gravitational force increases with inclination so does entrainment of ambient water. The upstream water masses entering the front moves with a velocity 60% higher. In other words, 40% of the main stream velocity causes mixing at the front.

Modelling of gravity currents ranges from simple numerical steady state stream tube models on an incline (Killworth, 1977; Alendal et al., 1994; Jungclaus et al., 1995) to full CFD simulations with topography (Jungclaus et al., 1995). The stream tube models were popular during the last decade because of their simplicity and low demand for computer power. They are usually one dimensional, in the along stream direction, and include influences from gravity, frictional, and rotational forces in addition to mixing due to

entrainment. It has been shown that the steady state assumption breaks down when the current speed approaches the phase velocity of waves on the current/ambient interface (Alendal et al., 1994; Alendal, 1995). Also for some flows it is necessary to include changes in stream tube height along the path and cross-stream variations (Borenäs and Wåhlin, 2000).

A gravity current will also be steered by bottom topography, an effect not present in the stream tube models. For instance, a gravity current flowing down a canyon will depending on time scale travel up on one side due to earth rotation. A temporal 3D model is required in order to include topographic effects. With the tools available, BOM (Berntsen, 2000) and MITgcm (Marshall et al., 1997b,a), it should be manageable to study a couple of scenarios where gravity currents flow down the continental slope on OL.

The picture is even more complex if sediments are suspended in the current. They will have an accelerating effect on the current due to increased density difference. To include this effect a proper settling/resuspension sub-model is required.

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: Medium.

Likelihood of success: Very high for stream tube modelling. High for CFD modelling.

Difficulty: Stream tube modeling easy, CFD modeling requires proper topographic treatment. Will benefit from the other activities related to topography.

Work requirements: Stream tube modeling: 2 months. CFD modeling 6 months to several years pending on required degree of accuracy and number of studies performed.

4.5 Risk of high current assessment by statistical methods.

Through the aforementioned activities and through the in-situ measurement program by the Ormen Lange consortium, a lot of data on current speed and direction will become available. By using a statistical method, frequently applied in studies on location and design of windmill power plants, a probability distribution on current speed can be built. This distribution can subsequently estimate probability, frequency and amplitude of high current events.

The method consist of fitting, through regression, the data with a current

speed distribution, often the Weibull or the log-Weibull distributions (Mann et al., 1974), by determining the unknown shape factors. Once a distribution is established it gives expected currents, and frequency and amplitude of rare events with high current speed that might jeopardise a pipeline.

Lun and Lam (2000) used the method for three different locations in Hong Kong using long term, thirty years, time series of hourly wind measurements. The three locations were used as a first step for establishing an adequate wind information data base for better predictions of wind related assessments.

Torres et al. (1999) describes a study on wind speed distribution and the most frequent wind directions for planning and designing of wind mill power plants. According to their paper and references therein the Weibull distribution has shown to give the best fit with wind speed data. One of their conclusions is that a power station situated in a wide channel show a clear dominant wind direction, as oppose to a plant in mountainous areas. Their approach might be useful for our studies on topographic steering and current fluctuations at OL.

Another study by Huang et al. (2001) evaluate long-term hurricane risk assessment in the southern United States. They develop a probabilistic hurricane event model with parameters derived from statistical analysis of storms including radius of maximum winds, central pressure difference, landfall location, storm track, and decay rate. Another interesting report published on the world wide web

(<http://www.oas.org/EN/cdmp/document/kma/coastal/coastrep.htm>) produce hurricane return period maps for the Caribbean. Based on our present understanding on the driving mechanisms at OL, the passage of storms, their extent, pressure gradient and track, a similar study would be interesting for ocean currents at OL.

Another benefit from such an exercise, by analysing both in-situ and numerical data in the same manner, a new comparison tool becomes available. In-situ data are usually time series of point measurements while numerical simulation data has spatial extent in addition to the temporal. It will be a valuable tool for model validation to have a statistical algorithm to see differences between the two classes of data sets in order to check consistency of the models.

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: High. Might introduce new methods for analysing model results and comparison

Likelihood of success: Medium to high pending on how deep into the material we go.

Work requirements: One year for establishing the framework and analysing

a selection of data sets. Once established new data sets can be analysed as they become available.

4.6 Correlations in neighbouring time series

Time series of currents and hydrography (temperature and salinity) at different locations at OL are essential to establish statistics on currents. The time series show, however, often erratic behaviour and it is often difficult to comprehend the events seen. In Vikebø et al. (2001a) the focus has been on three events giving peak values in the near bottom velocities. The events are related to travelling atmospheric low pressure systems, but there are also events that are not clearly coupled to the atmospheric pressure. Studying the time series of for instance velocities at different localities at OL, it is difficult to see any systematic time lags or correlations between neighbouring localities. However, systematic computations of the cross-correlation functions, see Emery and Thomson (1997), between different stations have not been performed so far. There are also measurements programs, overlapping in time with the time series at OL, for the Svinøy section close to the OL area in the southward direction, see Orvik et al. (2001). Comparisons and cross-correlations of Svinøy section and OL time series may contribute to the understanding of how waves and water masses are propagated along the shelf slope, and will be important when designing monitoring and forecasting systems. In particular possible correlations between the major events seen in neighbouring time series will be important.

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: Uncertain, depends on the outcome of the study.

Likelihood of success: Relatively high.

Difficulty: In principle fairly straightforward.

Work requirements: To work with these time series and to analyse them may be very time consuming. Each time series for a given position and depth should be related to all the others for that period for different depths at the same horizontal position and to time series at different depths at neighbouring positions. The time series should also be related to time series for the forcing. That is at least time series for wind or atmospheric pressure.

4.7 Maps of U-mean and U-max as function of Grad-P

Products that may be useful to the developers of OL would possibly be maps of expected values of current speeds, U_{mean} , and maps of expected extreme values of current speeds, U_{max} , as functions of lateral position and depth above sea bed. That is: For each lateral position vertical profiles of U_{mean} and U_{max} . Preliminary maps of this kind may be produced using existing time series and the insight gained from model studies. Such maps may be used as a priori estimates of U_{mean} and U_{max} when there are no further knowledge about the forcing of the system. The estimates of U_{mean} will probably be relatively good. However, to developers of the gas field the quality of the estimates of U_{max} may be more important. At present these estimates will be based on observations containing relatively few extreme events. The observations are filtered in time, and they are too sparse in space to capture all relevant spatial scales. Thus, estimates of U_{max} will probably be very uncertain.

Longer time series at several positions, preferably with better time resolution, may be used to improve the quality of the Weibull statistics and thus the estimates of U_{max} . Also repeated model experiments where the forcing is chosen from distributions of atmospheric and internal pressure may be used to produce statistics about U_{mean} and U_{max} .

In reality velocities and their maxima are strongly related to the gradients in the pressure as discussed above. Thus with more precise information about atmospheric and internal pressure which we may have in forecasts for a few days, also more precise estimates of U_{mean} and U_{max} for the next few days may be produced. These statistics may be produced for instance through repeated model simulations where the strength of forcing is given, but the specific pathway of the pressure disturbance chosen randomly.

Importance to the OL activity: High.

General scientific importance: Probably low.

Likelihood of success: Relatively high.

Difficulty: In principle fairly straightforward.

Work requirements: It will be time consuming to produce the maps and to make them easily accessible to the users.

5 Conclusions

Activities on a wide range of scientific issues and related tasks, involving a large group of people, are thus possible to improve the present understanding

of currents and current profiles at OL. Some activities may involve laboratory experiments and require physical models, for some studies also rotating tables, and such experiments may be performed by competent research groups in Oslo and/or Trondheim. Other activities involve analysis of measured time series. Such analysis may be performed by the present research group, but should preferably be done by oceanographers that are more familiar with analysing field data.

The present research group may perform relevant model studies on a range of spatial scales. Problem areas that may be addressed include:

- a) Topographical steering (Holloway, 1992),
- b) Parametrisation of drag from sub-grid scale topographical features,
- c) Further model nesting with focus on OL,
- d) Idealised studies of internal waves/run-ups,
- e) Studies of gravity currents with realistic topography,
- f) Establishing necessary statistics to produce U_{mean} and U_{max} ,
- g) Maps of current profiles of U_{mean} and U_{max} .

Further activities on the topics above will be relevant to OL, and they may contribute to the basic understanding of physical processes outside the shelf break.

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